

Steel Coil Loads acting on Inner Hull in Heel Condition

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Abstract. Ships, such as bulk carriers or general cargo ships, intending to carry steel coils need to be subjected to structural strength evaluations specifically for the loads generated by such coils when designing hull structures because said loads are concentrated loads that differ from the pressures typically generated by bulk cargo and ballast water. Although the IACS Common Structural Rules (CSR) does specify requirements for the scantlings of inner hulls in consideration of such loads, its requirements are mainly based on industry research carried out in Japan during the 1970s, research that is commonly referred to as SR166. This research did show experimental and numerical calculation results for the heel condition for cases in which steel coils are arranged in a single tier, but it makes no mention combinations of heel conditions and cases in which steel coils are arranged in two or more tiers. Moreover, the research focused on the loads acting on vertical walls in the heel condition but did not examine the loads acting on the bilge hopper plating of bulk carriers. In this study, the authors used non-linear FE analysis considering contact and friction of steel coils to reproduce the loads examined by SR166. In addition, the loads acting on the inner hull in the heel condition were then examined under those loading conditions deemed likely to occur during actual operations involving steel coils arranged into two or three tiers. The study found that the loads acting on walls, including those on the hopper side, were smaller than the product of the total weight of the coils at a designated heel angle in all cases due to the rotation of the coils being stopped by friction, which was itself acting as a stopper.

Keywords: *Steel coils, Loads acting on inner hull, Heel condition, and Non-linear FEM*

1. Introduction

Ships, such as bulk carriers and general cargo ships, intending to carry steel coils, which are long wound rolls of steel, need to be subjected to structural strength evaluations specifically for the loads generated by such coils when designing hull structures because said loads are concentrated loads that differ from the pressures typically generated by bulk cargo and ballast water. When steel coils are loaded, wooden dunnage is, in principle, laid in between the hull structure and steel coil, and key coils are placed to secure the cargo as shown in Figure 1. Furthermore, it is common to place some wedges (no image in Figure 1 but similar with wheel stopper) under the cargo at the lowest tier and use steel bands in order to secure the cargo [1].

Although the structural rules, such as the IACS Common Structural Rules (hereinafter, referred to as the “IACS CSR”), of classification societies do specify methods for considering steel coil loads [2], these methods are mainly based on research, commonly referred to as SR166, carried out by the shipbuilding industry in Japan during the 1970s [3][4]. SR166 did provide experimental and numerical calculation results for the 20-degree heel condition and those cases where steel coils are arranged in a single tier, but it makes no mention combinations of the heel condition and cases in which steel coils are arranged in two or more tiers. Moreover, SR166 only examined the steel coil loads acting on vertical walls but did not study the loads acting on the bilge hopper plating of bulk carriers.

In this study, the authors used non-linear FE analysis to consider the contact and friction of steel coils and dunnage, and then compared the results to those for steel coil loads observed by SR166. The steel coil loads acting on inner hulls (both vertical walls and hopper slopes) in the heel condition were then calculated under various loading conditions (i.e. steel coil arrangements) that are likely to occur in actual operations involving steel coils arranged into two or three tiers. That is, the combination of two/three-tiers and vertical walls and the combination of single/two/three-tiers and hopper slopes are newly investigated in the heel condition.

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Figure 1. Example of means for securing steel coils [2]

2. Past study by the shipbuilding research association of Japan (SR166)

In 1978, a research committee of the shipbuilding research association of Japan, commonly known as SR166, investigated steel coil loads and how the structural response due to said loads should be considered with respect to hull structural design. SR166 investigated and proposed the following items:

- (1) steel coil loads acting on inner bottoms to consider the effect of dunnage;
- (2) steel coil loads acting on side walls in the heel condition to consider the effect of friction; and
- (3) strength evaluation of the hull structural members on which (1) and (2) above act.

This study focused on (2) above because the wooden dunnage and hull structure examined in (1) and (3) are similar to those examined in the 1970s, and the characteristics to be considered for hull structural design were expected to be the same.

With regard to (2) above, SR166 carried out experiments in which the steel coil loads acting on side walls were measured in the 20-degree heel condition (Figure 2) with a roll period of 60 seconds. The position of key coil was changed from $m = 1$ to $m = 8$, and the height of the key coil was changed from $a/D = 1/6$ to $a/D = 1/2$ (Figure 3). SR166 found that the loads acting on side walls in the heel condition were less than the gravity component of the total coil weight; that is, they were less than the product of the weight of ten coils and 9.81 m/s^2 times the sine of 20 degrees, due to the effect of friction. Figure 4 shows the experimental results in the 20-degree heel condition and the associated calculation results (further described in the appendix) obtained by solving the equilibrium of force of each coil. The horizontal axis represents the number of coils, m and n , counted from the key coil (see also Figure 2), while the vertical axis, C_k , shows the steel coil loads acting on the side wall divided by the product of the weight of one coil and the sine of 20 degrees. It observed that C_k strongly depends on the location of the key coil, and the steel coil loads correspond to only a maximum of three coils acting on the side wall even though ten coils are arranged.

Figure 2. Experimental model for measuring steel coil loads used by SR166

Figure 3. Definition of height parameters a and D of key coil

Figure 4. Steel coil loads acting on a side wall [5]

3. Non-linear FEM and comparison with SR166

A model simulating SR166 was developed and non-linear FE analysis was performed using the commercial analysis software MSC Marc 2021.1. As shown in Figure 5, ten coils in total were arranged with a key coil under the condition of $a/D = 1/2$, $m = 4$ and $n = 5$. Dunnage was installed on a rigid body simulating a floor, and side walls were fixed to the rigid body. Table 1 shows the details of the coils, dunnage and side wall.

The analysis used a dynamic implicit method that considered geometric non-linearity and contact (node to segment), and the bilinear Coulomb friction model was used to take the effect of friction into account.

Gravitational acceleration was gradually increased up to 100 % over 10 seconds from the beginning of the calculation, with the rigid body being rotated at the speed shown in Figure 6 around the center of rotation shown in Figure 5 for the next 100 seconds. In other words, it was heeled up to 20 degrees so that the Coil C01 coil was down, and then heeled at 20 degrees so that the Coil C09 was down. Table 1 shows other calculation conditions.

Figure 5. Calculation model: Overview (left) and details in way of contact points (right)

Figure 6. Time history of rotation speed of a rigid body

Although a coefficient of friction should be defined for this non-linear FEM, information related to it cannot be found in SR166. An example of the friction coefficient between wood and steel can be found in reference [6], but it is difficult to identify such a value in SR166 due to the effects of surface roughness, humidity, etc.

Table 1. Calculation conditions

	Steel coil	Dunnage	Side wall
Dimension	Outer diameter: 475 mm Depth: 200 mm	Thickness: 10 mm Depth (width): 60 mm (corresponds to two pieces of dunnage, each 30 mm in depth)	Thickness: 12 mm Depth: 750 mm
Elastic modulus	206000 N/mm ²	109 N/mm ² Elasto-plastic is considered so that yield stress is 2.35 N/mm ²	206000 N/mm ²
Poisson ratio	0.3	0.3	0.3
Density	7.054 × 10 ⁻⁶ kg/mm ³	0.53 × 10 ⁻⁶ kg/mm ³	7.8 × 10 ⁻⁶ kg/mm ³
Mesh size	min. 1 mm × 1 mm	min. 1 mm × 1 mm	min. 1 mm × 1 mm

SR166 also mentions additional theoretical investigations related to solving the equilibrium of force as described in the appendix. These investigations reported the theoretical result represented as the dot line in Figure 4 (as “calculation”). Based upon this theoretical approach, the coefficient of friction between coils, μ , is derived to be 0.42; however, since μ between coil and dunnage was not relevant to the calculation result, no specific value can be found. Hence, the authors decided to consider $\mu = 0.4$, which is close to 0.42, for between coils in the non-linear FE analysis. The cases of $\mu = 0.6$ and 0.8 were also considered as sensitive analyses, and the coefficient between coil and dunnage was taken as the same value as μ for between coils.

Figure 7 shows the history of steel coil loads acting on a side wall and a comparison with SR166. It was found that the cases of $\mu = 0.6$ and 0.8 have good agreement from the beginning of calculation to the timing of 20-degree heel that Coil C01 is down, compared to SR 166. On the other hand, the case of $\mu = 0.4$ shows larger steel coils loads on the side wall in comparison to the other two cases. Figure 8 shows part of the result of the $\mu = 0.4$ case, which is normal contact force and friction force of Coil C03 (the third coil from the side wall) at a position between dunnage and the coil. The solid lines represent the results of the non-linear FE analysis, and the dotted lines represent values obtained from the theoretical value based on the approach described in the appendix. Gray lines (solid and dotted) represent values obtained when friction forces are divided by normal contact forces, with the dotted gray line (theoretical values) exceeding 0.4 when the heel is large. It was observed the value exceeds 0.4 in some coils, that is, it means the coils slip on the dunnage. On the other hand, as shown in Figures 9 and 10, the value in the cases of $\mu = 0.6$ and 0.8 is less than the given friction coefficient even at maximum heel. The authors think this explains the discrepancy found in $\mu = 0.4$ case since it is assumed coils did not slip on the dunnage in SR166.

Figure 7. Steel coil loads acting on a side wall obtained by non-linear FEM

Figure 8. Contact normal force and friction force at a position between Coil C03 and dunnage ($\mu = 0.4$)

Figure 9. Contact normal force and friction force at a position between Coil C03 and dunnage ($\mu = 0.6$)

Figure 10. Contact normal force and friction force at a position between Coil C03 and dunnage ($\mu = 0.8$)

4. Steel coil loads acting on inner hulls under a two- or three-tier loading condition

Steel coil loads acting on a vertical side wall in the two- and three-tier loading condition and the loads acting on bilge hopper plating for one to three tiers were examined by the nonlinear FE analysis in similar way with the previous section.

Figures 11 to 17 show the coil arrangements used in the calculation model. The arrangement of steel coils in the two- and three-tier loading condition were decided in reference to industry standards [7], and some left-right asymmetric models were created to investigate the effect of asymmetry on the coil arrangement. The size and weight of the coil were taken as 1500 mm in outer diameter, 1500 mm in depth (width), and 15 tonnes so as to be close to actual hull structure design conditions. Two pieces of dunnage 30 mm in thickness and 130 mm in depth (width) were considered, and the dunnage was attached to the rigid body simulating inner bottom and the side wall (bilge hopper plating or longitudinal bulkhead).

Table 2 shows calculation conditions regarding a/D , the angle of bilge hopper plating to horizontal plane, and the friction coefficient μ . In order to investigate the effect of the height position of the key coil, several a/D patterns were examined for case 1, including unrealistic patterns such as 0.13, and the effects of the angles of bilge hopper plating (30, 45, and 60 degrees), were investigated. Since the coefficient of friction in reality is considered to vary widely for reasons mentioned in the previous section as well as other factors such as paper packing for cargo protection, the authors did not consider it appropriate to assign an unambiguous value to μ ; hence, the authors varied the μ between coils in the range of 0.3 to 0.5. There may also be various possibilities regarding μ between coil and dunnage in actual practice because the operators of a ship should, in principle, not only install key coils but also lashing between the coils, and also insert chocks so that the coils do not slide, from the viewpoint of cargo securing; thus, μ between the coil and dunnage was considered as 0.6 except for Case 4-2.

A roll angle of 20 *degrees* for a period of 13 *seconds* was considered in which starboard was first down 20 *degrees* and then port was down 20 *degrees*. Other calculation conditions were the same as those in the previous section.

Figure 11. Calculation models for Case 1 (top and left), Case 1a (top and right), and Case 1b (bottom)

Figure 12. Example of hopper plate with angle of 30 *degrees*

Figure 13. Calculation models for Case 2 (left) and Case 2a (right)

Figure 14. Calculation model for Case 3

Figure 15. Calculation model for Case 4

Figure 18 shows a von-Mises stress distribution for Cases 3-1, 3-2, and 3-3 at the timing of the 20-*degree* heel; the steel coil load acting on the side wall (red arrow and text); and the friction force between the dunnage and the coil (blue arrow and text). The effect of the difference in the friction coefficient between the coils was not large for any of the values. In addition, the steel coil loads acting on the side wall were around $2.2Wg$ (where W represents the mass of a single coil and g represents gravitational acceleration) in these cases, and said loads were about 25 % of gravity component of the total coil weight ($25Wg \text{ times the sine of } 20 \text{ degrees} = 8.6Wg$). Since the ratio is within the range of the past research, i.e. Ck in Figure 4, it suggests the findings of SR166 are valid also for the two-tier loading condition. This phenomenon is considered to be caused by the rotation of steel coils being locked due to friction and is expected to be similar to the behavior exhibited by a car or bicycle when its applying the brake to lock its tires on a slope.

Table 2. Calculation conditions

Case ID	a/D	Hopper angle (deg.)	μ (b/w coils)	Other
Case 1-1	0.13	45	0.42	
Case 1-2	0.19	45	0.42	
Case 1-3	0.33	45	0.42	
Case 1-4	0.50	45	0.42	
Case 1-5	0.69	45	0.42	
Case 1-6	0.89	45	0.42	
Case 1a-1	0.5	45	0.42	
Case 1a-2	0.5	30	0.42	
Case 1a-3	0.5	60	0.42	
Case 1b	0.5	45	0.42	
Case 2-1	0.5	45	0.42	
Case 2-2	0.5	45	0.3	
Case 2-3	0.5	45	0.5	
Case 2-4	0.5	30	0.42	
Case 2-5	0.5	60	0.42	Those coils in the second tier contacting the hopper plate as well as coils adjacent to them were analyzed for both the “with contact” and “without contact” cases.
Case 2a	0.5	45	0.42	
Case 3-1	0.5	90 (vertical)	0.42	
Case 3-2	0.5	90 (vertical)	0.3	
Case 3-3	0.5	90 (vertical)	0.5	
Case 4-1	0.5	90 (vertical)	0.3	
Case 4-2	0.5	90 (vertical)	0.42	$\mu = 0.4$ (between coil and dunnage)
Case 4-3	0.5	90 (vertical)	0.42	Lashing 1 ton
Case 4-4	0.5	90 (vertical)	0.42	Lashing 10 tonnes
Case 5	0.5	60	0.42	
Case 5a	0.5	60	0.42	One coil on the right side is removed from Case 5.
Case 5b	0.5	60	0.42	
Case 6	0.5	90 (vertical)		

Figure 16. Calculation models for Case 5 (top), Case 5a (middle) and Case 5b (bottom)

Figure 17. Calculation model for Case 6

Although the experimental and numerical analysis of SR166 were not carried out in the case of multiple tiers, it did propose that steel coil loads acting on side walls in multiple tiers be taken as the value obtained by multiplying the gravity component of the total coil weight by 0.7 (i.e. $8.6Wg \times 0.7$ in the case of Figure 18) as guidance for hull structural design because doing so considered the effect of friction. This correction factor 0.7 is based on a two-tiers loading condition to which the theoretical approach can be applied, however, the condition is an unrealistic condition that steel coils at the lowest tier do not contact each other. If the contact between them is taken into account, the steel coil load is expected to be smaller than the value according to the guidance of SR166. In fact, the non-linear analysis results the authors observed were sufficiently smaller than those proposed by SR166.

Figure 18. The von-Mises stress, steel coil load acting on a side wall, and friction force on dunnage: Case 3-1 (top), Case 3-2 (middle), and Case 3-3 (bottom)

5. Discussion

From the analysis of the previous section, it was observed that the steel coil loads acting on the side wall were sufficiently smaller than the products of the weight of the total number of coils and the sine of 20 degrees , even in the case of multi-tiers with respect to both side walls and hopper plates.

Since it was observed that the steel coil load changed due to differences in coil arrangement, a/D , μ , etc., a hull structural design approach which takes these effects into account is one possibility; such an approach, however, is likely to be difficult since said parameters need to be controlled during the actual operations of a ship. For this reason, it is preferable to consider those conditions which cover the results of various cases, i.e. that is the same as the conclusion of SR166. It is expected that the coefficient Ck (see Figure 4) found in SR166 is compatible to any case.

Hence, formulae of steel coil loads are proposed as Equations (1) and (2) for hull structural design; moreover, since the static load in still water and the dynamic load due to ship motions such as roll have been defined separately in hull structural strength evaluations of recent years, each of them is formulated as F_s and F_d , while F_{total} , the sum of F_s and F_d , is lastly considered for hull structural strength evaluation.

Vertical side walls such as longitudinal bulkheads are assessed as follows:

$$\begin{cases} F_{s,v} = 0 \\ F_{d,v} = C_k n_1 W g \sin \theta \\ F_{total,v} = F_{s,v} + F_{d,v} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where C_k is 3.2 when steel coils are either arranged in two or more tiers or arranged in one tier with the key coil located second or third from the side wall; for other cases, C_k is 2.0 for other cases. Furthermore, n_1 is the number of tiers. W is the mass of a single coil. g is gravitational acceleration. θ is the roll angle. Although the static load acting on the vertical wall is not zero per se, it can be taken as zero from a practical viewpoint since it is not a large value and is of little interest compared to total load.

For bilge hopper plating, a correction by the cosine function is added since it is appropriate to consider the steel coil loads in the normal direction to the hopper plating as described in proposal 1 of Equation (2). Since the affinity with the coefficient C_k of SR166 tends to decrease as it approaches the horizontal plane, another pattern of F_d , with 45 degrees as the lower limit in the correction by the cosine function is presented as proposal 2.

$$\begin{cases} F_{s,h} = C_0 W g \cos \alpha \\ F_{d,h} = C_k n_1 W g \sin \theta \cos \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \alpha \right) \\ \text{or} \\ = C_k n_1 W g \sin \theta \cos \left(\min \left(\frac{\pi}{4}, \frac{\pi}{2} - \alpha \right) \right) \\ F_{total,h} = F_{s,h} + F_{d,h} \end{cases} \quad \begin{matrix} \text{(proposal 1)} \\ \\ \text{(proposal 2)} \end{matrix} \quad (2)$$

Where α is the angle of bilge hopper plating to the horizontal plane, and C_0 is 1.0 for one tier, 1.1 for two tiers or where a key coil is placed at the second position from bilge hopper plating, and 1.2 for three tiers. In addition, C_0 is the tuned coefficient considering the distribution of the weight of the upper tiers to the lower tier in multiple tiers.

Figure 19 shows the relationship between the proposed formulae F_{total} and non-linear FE analysis results in the 20-degree condition for all the cases in Table 2, with the horizontal and vertical axes being normalized by Wg . These plots include the data of both starboard down and port side down, and the steel coil loads on starboard are plotted when starboard is down and said loads on port side are plotted when port side is down. Since the diameter of the coil is large enough compared to stiffened panels of the hull structure, and the two steel coil loads do not act simultaneously on the same stiffened panel, the steel coil load at each contact point is plotted in the figures for the case where two coils are in contact with the side wall as in Case 5 and Case 6.

Figure 19. Comparison between non-linear FE results and proposed formulae

Although both proposed equations generally cover the results of non-linear FE analysis, it should be noted that the proposal 1 formula may underestimate steel coil loads when the angle of bilge hopper plating is small; hence, using the proposal 2 formula is preferable for more conservative designs.

In addition, when determining F_d in hull structural design, it is expected to lead to a more strict evaluation if the inertia force generated by sway acceleration (lateral acceleration of ships) is taken into account, not only the change in the direction of gravitational acceleration due to roll. In this study, only roll angle is considered, and the calculation result for sway acceleration is not obtained. However, as mentioned above, since the steel coil loads acting on the sidewall are suppressed by the mechanism similar to car braking by locking the rotation of the coil due to friction, it is expected that the same effect is generated for sway acceleration as for the steel coil loads. Hence, it is considered that there is no practical problem to consider not only roll angle but also sway acceleration in F_d of the proposed formulae.

6. Conclusion

Nonlinear FE analysis considering contact and friction of steel coils and dunnage was carried out and the results were compared to the steel coil loads acting on side wall given in SR166. It was observed the steel coil loads had good agreement with SR 166 and theoretical investigation when the coils do not slip on dunnage.

In addition, steel coil loads were further investigated for various loading patterns by changing coil arrangements and some parameters, such as key coil height, using the non-linear FE analysis. The steel coil loads acting on vertical side walls and hopper plating for the one- to three-tier loading conditions were found to be always less than the gravity component of the total coil weight. This phenomenon is considered to be caused by the rotation of steel coils being locked due to friction and is expected to be similar to the behavior exhibited by a car or bicycle when applying its brake to lock its tires on a slope.

Based upon the above investigations, the authors proposed one formula for steel coil loads acting on vertical wall in multi-tier loading condition: that is almost the same formula format as one of SR166. And we also proposed two formulae for said loads acting on bilge hopper plating in one- to three-tier loading condition: one with a lower limit corrected by a cosine function and the other without any limit, and both are also the same format as SR166 except the cosine function. Although both proposed formulae generally agree with the results of the non-linear FE analysis, proposal 2, which has the lower limit, is considered preferable for reasons of conservative design.

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Appendix

In SR166 [3], steel coil loads for one-tier loading were estimated based on a theoretical approach, separate from experiments. Where three coils are placed on a slope, as shown in Figure 20, the balance of force in coils A, B, and C can be expressed as Equations (3), (4), and (5).

$$\begin{cases} W \cos \theta = F_{1A} + f_{2A} - F_{3A} \sin \varphi - f_{3A} \cos \varphi \\ W \sin \theta = F_{2A} + f_{1A} - F_{3A} \cos \varphi + f_{3A} \sin \varphi \\ 0 = f_{2A} + f_{3A} - f_{1A} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{cases} W \cos \theta = F_{3A} \sin \varphi + f_{3A} \cos \varphi + F_{2C} \sin \varphi + f_{2C} \cos \varphi \\ W \sin \theta = F_{3A} \cos \varphi - f_{3A} \sin \varphi - F_{2C} \cos \varphi + f_{2C} \sin \varphi \\ 0 = f_{3A} - f_{2C} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{cases} W \cos \theta = F_{1C} - f_{3C} - F_{2C} \sin \varphi - f_{2C} \cos \varphi \\ W \sin \theta = f_{1C} - F_{3C} + F_{2C} \cos \varphi - f_{2C} \sin \varphi \\ 0 = f_{2C} - f_{1C} + f_{3C} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Figure 20. Forces acting on coils

When the equilibrium of force is obtained under the condition in which the left end of the Coil A and the right end of the Coil C can slide according to Equation (6), the force at each position can be obtained by Equation (7).

$$\begin{cases} f_{2A} = \mu \cdot F_{2A} \\ f_{3C} = \mu \cdot F_{3C} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{cases} F_{1A} = W \sin \theta \left(\frac{3}{2} \cot \theta + \frac{1}{2} \tan \varphi - \frac{3\mu}{1+\mu} \right) - \frac{1-\mu}{1+\mu} \cdot \mu \cdot F_{3C} \\ f_{1A} = W \sin \theta \left[\frac{1}{1+\sin \varphi} \left(\frac{1}{2} \cos \varphi \cot \theta - \frac{3}{2} \sin \varphi \right) + \frac{3\mu}{1+\mu} \right] + F_{3C}(1-\mu) \left(\frac{\mu}{1+\mu} - \frac{\sin \varphi}{1+\sin \varphi} \right) \\ F_{2A} = \frac{1}{1+\mu} [3W \sin \theta + F_{3C}(1-\mu)] \\ f_{2A} = \mu F_{2A} \\ F_{3A} = \frac{1}{\cos \varphi} \left[W \left(\frac{1}{2} \cos \theta \cos \varphi - \frac{3}{2} \sin \theta \sin \varphi + 2 \sin \theta \right) + F_{3C}(1-\mu)(1-\sin \varphi) \right] \\ f_{3A} = \frac{1}{1+\sin \varphi} \left[W \left(\frac{1}{2} \cos \theta \cos \varphi - \frac{3}{2} \sin \theta \sin \varphi \right) - F_{3C}(1-\mu) \sin \varphi \right] \\ F_{1C} = W \sin \theta \left(\frac{3}{2} \cot \theta - \frac{1}{2} \tan \varphi \right) + \mu F_{3C} \\ f_{1C} = \frac{1}{1+\sin \varphi} \left[W \sin \theta \left(\frac{3}{2} \sin \varphi - \frac{1}{2} \cos \varphi \cot \theta \right) + (\mu + \sin \varphi) F_{3C} \right] \\ F_{2C} = \frac{1}{\cos \varphi} \left[W \left(\frac{1}{2} \cos \theta \cos \varphi - \frac{3}{2} \sin \theta \sin \varphi + \sin \theta \right) + F_{3C}(1-\mu)(1-\sin \varphi) \right] \\ f_{2C} = \frac{1}{1+\sin \varphi} \left[W \left(\frac{1}{2} \cos \theta \cos \varphi - \frac{3}{2} \sin \theta \sin \varphi \right) + F_{3C}(1-\mu) \sin \varphi \right] \\ f_{3C} = \mu F_{3C} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

When n coils are arranged on the right side of the key coil (Coil B), the load acting on the left side of Coil A is obtained by Equation (8).

$$F_{3c} = W \sin \theta \cdot \frac{1}{2\mu} \left[1 - \left(\frac{1-\mu}{1+\mu} \right)^{n-1} \right] + \left(\frac{1-\mu}{1+\mu} \right)^{n-1} F_0 \quad (8)$$

where F_0 means the force acting on the rightmost coil.